

Promising entries from the multiple resistance screening trial against GM and BPH. Cuttack, India, 1983 kharif.

Entry	Silvershoots (%)	GM-infested hills (%)	BPH resistance score ^a
RP2068-18-3-5	0	0	1
RP2068-17-3-7	0	0	7
RP2068-18-4-5	0	0	3
RP2068-18-2-6	0	0	7
RP2068-16-9-5	0	0	9
RP2068-18-4-7	0	0	9
Rp2068-18-2-11	0	4	7
TN1	40	100	9
IET8868 (OR 405-4)	0	0	7
IET7800	0	0	—
IET8371	0	0	1
RP2199-84-2	4	4	7
IR4707-106-3-2	29	77	7
RP2071-18-1-1	48	96	3
RP2076-464-2	40	92	3
TN1	26	100	9
RP2069-34-1-2	40	96	3
RP2068-12-1-8-1	28	96	1
RP2068-15-1-4-2	0	0	7
RP1579-28	0	0	9
RP1579-43	0	0	—
RP1579-48	4	4	7
RP1579-53	0	0	9
TN1	32	100	9

^aBy SES.

transplanting), and installing lights. Damage (% silvershoots and % infested hills) was graded when infestation peaked.

The same entries were tested for BPH resistance in the greenhouse by the bulk seedling screening method. Damage was graded on the 0–9 scale of the *Standard evaluation system for rice (SES)*.

Thirteen cultivars were highly resistant to GM (see table). Three cultivars — RP2068-18-2-11, RP2199-84-2, and RP1579-48 — had less than 5% infestation. A strong correlation was observed between percentage of silvershoots and percentage of infested hills ($r = 0.786$).

Seven entries were resistant to BPH (score 1–3): and three — RP2068-18-3-5, RP2068-4-4-5, and IET8371 — were resistant to both GM and BPH. The RP2068 cultivars were derived from the cross Swarnadhan/ Veluthachem, while IET8371 came from the cross Phalguna/ARC6650, deriving their dual resistance from known donors. *ℵ*

Varietal resistance of rice to leaffolder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*

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Rice leaffolder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* is a major pest in India, causing 80% yield loss in rice. We screened 18 rice accessions from AICRIP for resistance to leaffolder by a seedling screening technique at the Paddy Breeding Station, TNAU, Coimbatore, and in field trials at Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Pondichery, during 1984 kharif.

Pregerminated seeds of test accessions were sown 6 cm apart in 6 rows in 50 × 40 × 10 cm wooden seedboxes. Each accession was planted in a replication across the width of the seedbox in such a way to maintain at least 5 hills (3 plants/hill) per row. One row of susceptible check TN1 and two rows with resistant checks ASD11 and PTB33 were sown at random in the seedboxes.

Leaffolder resistance in rice accessions.

Rice accession	Cross/Parents	Damage rating	
		Glasshouse (Coimbatore)	Field (Pondicherry)
RP 2068-18-2-9	Swarnadhan/Veluthachera	3	1
RP 2068-184-2	Swarnadhan/Veluthachera	5	3
RP 2068-18-4-5	Swarnadhan/Veluthachera	3	3
IR4707-106-3-2	IR1888-156/IR2061-213-2	3	3
	IR1561-228-3-3		
Bangelei	Donor	5	3
ARC 6650	Donor	3	3
CO 29	Donor	5	3
PTB 12	Donor	5	3
TNAU LFR831333	Vaigai/ARC 10550	5	3
TNAU LFR832036	IR20/ARC 10550	3	1
TNAU LFR832038	IR20/Vazhaippoo Samba	5	3
TNAU LFR831311	CO 41/BKNBR1088-83	3	1
TNAU LFR832035	CO 41/BKNBR1088-83	3	3
TNAU LFR831331	Bhavani/T2005	3	3
ARC10660	Donor	3	3
W 1263	Donor	5	1
TKM 6	Donor	5	3
IET 5741	Imp. Sab./Sona	3	3
ASD11	(Resistant check)	3	—
FTB33	(Resistant check)	3	—
TN1	(Susceptible check)	9	5

On the 7th day of seeding the wooden seedboxes were transferred to iron trays (62 × 47 × 15 cm) filled with 5 cm of water. Twenty days after seeding, the plants in the seedboxes were covered

with rectangular nylon net cages into which field-collected leaffolder moths were released continuously for 3 d at 20 moths/cage (♂:♀ 1:1). A cotton swab soaked in 1% sugar solution was hung

inside the cage as food for the moths. Moths were allowed to oviposit for 3-4 d. Fifteen days after release of the moths, the leafroller damage was assessed by counting the number of damaged leaves with reference to total leaves in each row, and infestation percentage was calculated. Based on

infestation percentage, the accessions were rated for damage using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

The same accessions were screened in the field in two replications, at Pondicherry where leafroller infestation was high.

Accessions RP2068-18-4-5, IR4707-

106-3-2, ARC6650, ARC10660, TNAU LFR832035, and TNAU LFR831331 had a damage rating of 3 both in seedling screening and in the field. RP2068-18-2-9, TNAU LFR832036, and TNAU LFR 831311 had a score of 3 in seedling screening and 1 in the field (see table). *S*

Promising long-duration lowland rices with resistance to key insect pests of kharif rice

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Host plant resistance to insect pests and diseases is the key to increased productivity of lowland kharif rice. Several promising lines from the crosses CR260 (CR151-79/CR1014), CR254 (Haldia-Magura/CR151-79), CR256

(Haldia-Magura/Pankaj) and CRM10 (Mahsuri mutant) adapted to lowlands (water stagnation of up to 60 cm), of long duration (145-180 d), and with good grain quality and high yields (3-5 t/ha) were identified in recent years at CRRI. In wet season, however, the yellow stem borer *Scirpophaga incertulas* Walker and the gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason limit production in many rice tracts. Pest-resistant cultivars can stabilize rice yields in these regions. We identified such cultivars from a set of 72 promising lines

from the above crosses.

In six cultivars of CR260 grown in lowlands at CRRI in 1981 and 1982 kharif together with yield standards in replicated trials, stem borer incidence at heading was very high, up to 28.5% whiteheads (WH) in 1981 and 27.6% in 1982. Cultivar CR260-30 was outstanding and superior to the others with zero WH in 1981 and 0.3% in 1982.

In 1983 kharif, all 72 lines were field tested. Plants were infested by implanting 4 healthy, laboratory-laid 4-d-old borer egg masses per plant on 4 growing plants per cultivar 50-75 d after planting (DAP) (2 at 50-55 DAP, 1 at 65 DAP, and 1 at 75 DAP). Percentage of deadhearts (DH) was as high as 78.8; WH, 75.8; and gross borer infestation, 77.3. The following cultivars were identified as outstandingly superior to the others and superior to or on par with the resistant checks: CR260-163-238, CR260-151-81-2-710, CR260-176-1-702, CR260-167-247-179, CR260-228, and CR260-30 (Table 1). Sashyashree released as resistant to stem borer was highly susceptible with the egg mass implantation technique.

We tested all 72 cultivars in another replicated field trial in 1983 kharif. Plants were transplanted in Jul at 15 × 15 cm spacing, with high fertilizer input (150 + 50 + 50 kg N/ha). Lights were installed and 3-5 cm standing water was maintained to induce high gall midge infestation (up to 100% infested hills and 39.3% silvershoots) in susceptible Jaya. Although no entry was highly resistant, CR260-21-2-716, CR260-21-715, CR254-43-126, CR256-31-36, CR254-43-42-3, and CR260-30 were the least susceptible and significantly superior to the other cultivars and the susceptible check (Table 2).

Table 1. Some promising stem borer-resistant late-duration cultivars with implantation of egg masses on growing plants in field, kharif 1983, CRRI.^a

Cultivar	DH (%)	WH (%)	Infestation (%)	Height (cm)	Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)	Grain type
CR260-163-238	21.3	2.6	15.0	120	150	4.5	LS
CR260-151-81-2-710	14.3	nil	9.7	115	145	3.5	MS
CR260-176-1-702	22.4	3.1	17.3	125	150	4.0	MS
CR260-167-247-179	23.0	nil	10.0	125	155	4.0	MS
CR256-30-211-2-708	58.7	14.3	47.9	120	155	3.5	MS
CR260-151-224	80.0	nil	76.4	120	155	4.5	LS
CR260-228	29.6	NA	29.6	120	150	4.0	LS
CR260-30	22.5	5.0	17.4	130	185	4.5	MS
IR9828-23-1 (R check)	27.0	22.2	25.0				
IR15723-45-3-2-2-2 (R check)	28.6	27.8	28.0				
Jaya (S check)	51.7	73.1	61.8				
Sashyashree	78.8	75.8	77.3				

^aR = resistant, S = susceptible, DH = deadhearts, WH = whiteheads, NA = not available, LS = long slender, MS = medium slender.

Table 2. Some promising gall midge-tolerant late-dulation cultivars. CRRI, 1983 kharif.

Cultivar	Mean % silvershoots	Angular values	Height (cm)	Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)	Grain type ^a
CR260-21-2-716	14.6	22.43	110	145	4.0	MS
CR260-21-7 15	15.1	22.72	110	145	4.0	MS
CR254-43-126	12.4	21.50	130	155	4.5	SB
CR256-31-36	12.7	20.55	100	140	4.0	SB
CR254-43-42-3	12.5	22.73	130	155	4.0	SB
CR260-30	11.3	19.36	130	185	4.5	MS
CR260-85-230	31.7	34.23	120	160	4.0	MS
Jaya (susceptible check)	39.3		90	135	3.0	LB
CD 0.05		7.25				
CD 0.01		9.62				

^aMS = medium slender, SB = short bold, LB = long bold.